

SOME CONSIDERSTIONS ABOUT PAST AND PRESENT OF UZBEK SCIENCE
LANGUAGE

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Аннотация: Мақолада миллий тил тараққиётида адабий-бадиий ҳамда илмий тилнинг тугган ўрни ҳақида сўз юритилган. Илмий услуб ва академ тилнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари таҳлил қилинган. Аждодларимиз илмий мерослари ўзга академ тилларда ёзилганлигининг узоқ ва яқин тарихига мурожаат қилинган. Мамлакатимиз раҳбари томонидан Давлат тилига қаратилаётган эътибор ўзбек академ тилини оёққа тургизишда асосий омил бўлиши таъкидланган. Илмий тил – миллий тилни мукамалликка эришиши ва абадийликка муҳрланишида асосий омил эканлигини асослашга эътибор қаратилган.

Калит сўзлар: она тили, илмий услуб, илмий тил, академ тил, академ манба, тил аудиторияси, адабий-бадиий тил, миллий тил, тил эгалари, ўзга тил, жонли тил, илмий таҳлил, илм, эскирган сўзлар.

Аннотация: В данной статье идёт речь о роли позиции литературно-художественного и научного языка в развитии национального языка. Были проанализированы особенности научного стиля и академического языка. Она адресовывается на научные наследия наших предков, которые были написаны на других академических языках. Отмечено, то, что уделяемое внимание со стороны Президента на государственный язык станет главным фактором в становлении узбекского академического языка. Подчёркивается, что научный язык служит для развития национального языка, и для достижения совершенства и бессмертия.

Ключевые слова: родной язык, научный стиль, научный язык, академический язык, академический источник, языковая аудитория, литературно-художественный язык, национальный язык, владельцы языка, иностранный язык, живой язык, научный анализ, наука, устаревшие слова.

Annotation: The article talks about the role of literary and scientific language in the development of the national language. Peculiarities of scientific style and academic language are

analyzed. It is addressed to the long and recent history of the scientific heritage of our ancestors which was written in other academic languages. It is noted that the attention paid to the State Language by the President of our country will be the main factor in establishing the Uzbek academic language. It is emphasized on justifying the fact that the scientific language is the main factor in the national language's achievement of perfection and immortality.

Key words: native language, scientific style, scientific language, academic language, academic source, language audience, literary language, national language, language owners, foreign language, alive language, scientific analysis, science, obsolete words.

It is obvious that one of the main signs of the nation is language. Although informal, the role of the national language on the stage of history as well as on an international level is, firstly, its formation as a literary-artistic language; secondly, it is conspicuous by its evolution in scientific, in particular, as Academ language. Both of these aspects are embodied - a double-winged language, as well as the status of the language's owners in the world civilization and the international community will be relatively stable. The percentage of voluntary learners of such a language, or benefactors of this language, is the majority. Such languages will have a decisive voice in the international community. Modern science and technology innovations reach others through them. The way of life of language owners is formed respectively.

Initially, on the issue of the formation of Uzbek language as a literary-artistic language, it should be said: from ancient times, thousands of years before the emergence of writing, the product of folk wisdom has passed from generation to generation through its representatives of nation, who had a very strong memory.

There are countless folk works worth to show to the world as *dostons, lapars, proverbs, fairytales, yor-yors, lullabies, season and ceremonial songs*, from written resources, starting with *Orkhon-Yenisey monuments, Kutadgu Bilig (Gracious Knowledge), Hibatul-Hakayik, Stories of the Prophets, and dozens, hundreds of classic masterpieces, wonderful ghazals were written, in our language, despite the fact that, our language was humiliated by others as "rude language".* The beauty of this language was proved only through the works of the Khazrat Navoiy. This phenomenon is found as a practical expression of the spiritual power of the vast kingdom founded by Sahibqiron Amir Temur through the works of Nizamiddin Mir Alisher Navoi by academician Aziz Qayumov¹. Simply put, the politics of the state established by Amir Temur

¹.Алишер Навоий 10 жилдли 1-жилд. Ғофур Ғулом номидаги нашриёт-матбаа ижод уйи. Тошкент 2012 й. 7-б.

introduced our language to the world as a literary-artistic language. Sealed it to immortality². That is to say – *Шеърят мулкида бўлди, Шоҳу султон, ўзбегим*³. While talking about Uzbek Academic language, it will be necessary to first clarify the phenomenon that is now called the scientific method, as well as the issues that can now be applied in the name of academic language as its perfection. In scientific style, In the scientific style, scientific concepts are given in a relatively popular form. To be even more precise-both phenomena have different audiences that are inextricably linked with each other. The audience of the scientific style: 1) activation in school textbooks from lower to upper classes; 2) a work of art, or scientific information provided by necessity in a particular source – its expression through units of the scientific style; 3) in the colloquial speech is limited with the desire to use a scientific style in order to clarify the issue of the subject in the communication process

The audience of the academic language: 1) the lesson in higher education and lectures, handbooks for students; 2) scientific works, dissertations and monographies; 3) scientific meetings and conferences, discussions of scientific works, meetings dedicated to seminars and protections of dissertations, sometimes also cover conversations between scientists.

A certain notion is given in the necessary case will be provided in particular form: *scientific method or academic language*. For example, in scientific method – *A number of words concerning to the scientific work will be provided.*, while in academic language – *As a core of the research particular linguistic unities will be analyzed.*, which reflects the uniqueness of both cases. Even if academic language is feed with the alive language, it is based on scientific analysis. According to this an academic language is completely different from the language that is used during the daily life.⁴ Any language unit becomes the property of the world of science by serving scientific accuracy in the structure of an academic language.

We will look through the topic of the *obsolete words* the analysis will be conducted according to the meaning of the words by putting them in order as a source of the research were taken subject books of 10th grade *Ona tili*⁵-(O.t.) and the book *Ҳозирги ўзбек адаби тили I қисм*⁶ (X.ў.а.т.):

².Амир Темир асос солган мустаҳкам давлатчилик сиёсати ва илмга бўлган жиддий эътиборнинг тизимли равишда узлуқиз давом этиш натижасида Алишер Навоий ижод қилган муҳит шаклланганлиги эътироф этилмоқда.

³.Воҳидов Э., Сайланма 1-жилд, Ўзбегим қасидаси “Шарқ” Тошкент 2000 й. 200-203-б.

⁴.Bailey A.L., Heritage M. Progressing students language day by day [Electronic resource] California: Sage: Corwin Press, 2019. 240 p. Electron dan. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781071873250.n5> (date of access: 19.12.2022).

⁵.Mengliyev B., Abdurahim Sh., Mavlonova K., va boshqalar. *Ona tili*, Umumiy o`rta ta`lim maktablarining 10-sinifi uchun darslik, Respublika ta`lim markazi. Toshkent 2022, 32-bet.

⁶.Шоабдурахмонов Ш., Асқарова М., Ҳожиёв А., ва бошқ. *Ҳозирги ўзбек адабий тили. I қисм. “Ўқитувчи”* Тошкент 1980, 125-бет.

I. *Words turn into obsolete one according to two reasons, that is, went out of use. (O.t.)*

II. *Obsolete words divided into two according to the main two features: (X.ŷ.a.t.)*

The first source (o.t.) from - ..., i.e., the general out of the sentence is a relative phenomenon. That is, the fact that many words, such as *вазир, ҳоким, вилоят, туман, талаба, ширкат, бекат*, which became obsolete in our language in the last century, have become again active in the years after independence, while words that outdated now may also be activated from time to time. Still, in the sense of not distracting a schoolboy, the sentence we have quoted from his textbook is clear and correct in time and space. After all, the requirements of academic language cannot be placed to a scientific-style source. The student in the next level – in higher education and in higher stages of education, can learn them from the second source which was mentioned above (H.o'.a.t).

1) disappearing the notions named after the words; (O.t.)

- *words denoting the historical events or things (that disappeared now)*; (X.ŷ.a.t.)

2) *instead of these words, another word(s) are actively applied, the loss of the need for it.* (O.t.)

- *currently existing (modern) thing or occasion's outdated term of phenomena (archaic words)*. (X.ŷ.a.t.)

The first source (o.t.) in (1) the extinction of the notion; sentences such as the (2) loss of the need has also disappeared in the recent past, the need has disappeared –hundreds of notions and words such as *qori, hadis, ulamo, jadid, tegirmon, ajuvoz, sumalak, halim*, reactivated after independence, indicate that the opinion in the quote is not correct. However, when it is observed from the point of view of the potential of a schoolboy, the theoretical opinions on the source should be considered as correct and appropriate. As we have pointed out, the Academ language requirement cannot be put beside a scientific-style source. Even the second source (H.o'.a.t.) created in the time of the Soviets, the sentences were formed according to the requirements of academic language so the theoretical information in it has not been shed.

The time gap between given sources which were published is about half a century. Moreover, two different political system, with different attitudes towards the Uzbek language, that it to say O.t. the development of national language is elevated to the state policy level; X.ŷ.a.t. was created when all opportunities of our language was limited, and humiliated. Nevertheless, it is not hard to see the accuracy of the academic language of one, which differs from another by its accuracy of the scientific style. Such examples can be cited from all fields of science, as much as you need.

The scientific style serves as the main factor in the formation of the "academic consciousness and its material form academ language – academ text"⁷ of the reader, in his mind." In this sense, the scientific style and the academic language, or rather the academic language and the scientific style can be mentioned as reality in a form of spiral, one of which assumes the other, which is interrelated to one another.

In order to highlight essence of the particular science fields the essence of emerging the term academic language becomes the demand of the time, such terms in our language as: Islamic Academy, Academy of Internal Affairs, Medical Academy, Academ Theater, Academy of Arts, and in order to highlight the exact point of view or item that it to say: academic edition; academic exchange, academic communication, academic hour, academic lyceum... in order to signify a point with scientific accuracy of a particular field, as a great example which highlights the power of the Uzbek language – the activation of Uzbek language by the name of the academic language which becomes a requirement of the time.

The academic language can not be defined as it was defined the literary language. In previous century old scientists in meetings sarcastically said: - *...there are two holy languages for us first is – Arabian language: the second is – Russian language. We cannot touch them. The Uzbek language we can “beat” as much as we want*⁸. The great poet towards this issue expressed his meaning: *Камалакдек ранго-ранг Бўлсин деб санъат, тиллер. Асрларча қилдик жанг, Армон қилдик минг йиллар*⁹.

Indeed, hundreds, thousands of scientist who created the cradle of World civilization, such as Al Farghani, Al Khwarazmiy, Al Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Mahmud Qoshgariy, Abunasr Farabi, az Zamahshariy, Burkhoniddin Marghinani, Al Bukhari, Mirzo Ulugbek, Ali Qushchi, their scientific works, books were written in Arabic language. They made their invaluable discoveries, even the main memoir of our native language, in 11th-century was written in an Arabic language¹⁰. As we noted, our scientific and spiritual heritage has been immortalized on history

⁷.Чернявская Я. Л. Академический язык: научный стиль речи в курсе русского языка как иностранного / Я. Л. Чернявская, А. Г. Шалабодова, О. И. Черных // Непрерывное образование: XXI век. - 2023. - Вып. 1 (41). - DOI:

⁸.Ўзбек тилида “арабча, русча сўзларни қўлланиши билан боғлиқ нуқсонлар ҳақда гапирманг: буларнинг орқасида босқичлар билан тил бириктирган мутассиб чала муллалар ва қонхўр империя турибди...” деган маънода.

⁹.Воҳидов Э., Сайланма. Шеър дунёси, иккинчи жилд. Она тилим ўлмайди, “Шарк” Тошкент 2001 й, 46-б.

¹⁰Маҳмуд Қошғарий, “Девону лугатит турк” Ўзбекистон Фанлар академияси “Фан” Тошкент 1960-1962 й. 3 жилдли, таржимон ва нашрга тайёрловчи С.М. Муталибов.

for centuries as a legacy of the Arab scientific world. After Arabic language, took the turn in an "estafeta" the Russian language. The legacy of great representatives of our literature, Zarifa Saidnosirova, Habib Abdullaev, Khodi Zarif, Ibrahim Mouminov, Hamid Sulaiman, Ayup Ghulam, Saadi Sirojiddinov, Fozila Sulaymanova, Vasil Qobulov, Hamdam Usmanov, Yakhyo Ghulomov, Suyima Ghanieva, Kadir Ghulomov, the dozens of books are internationally recognized as a product of the Russian scientific world.

Indeed, hundreds of the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the world Al Fargoni, Al Kharazmi, Al Beruni, Ibn Sino, Makhmud Kashgari, Abu Nasr Farabi, Az Zamakhshari, Burkhaniddin Marginani, Al Bukhari, Mirza Ulugbek, Ali Kushchi, have written their scientific works in science language of their time, Arabian language. They made their invaluable discoveries, even the source of the 11th-century memoir of our native language was written in Arabic¹¹. As we have mentioned, our scientific-literary legacy is accepted as the scientific legacy of Arabian scientific world. The Russian language took an estafeta, the scientific legacy of the great names as Zarifa Saidnosirova, Khabib Abdullaev, Khodi Zarif, Ibrakhim Muminov, Khamid Suleyman, Ayup Gulyam, Saadi Sirojiddinov, Fozila Sulaymonova, Vosil Kabulov, Khamdam Usmonov, Yakhyo Gulomov, the list of names itself, does not fit into dozens of books, is internationally recognized as a product of the Russian scientific world.

As poet mentioned: *Кимдир майда миллат бўлди, Кимдир катта*¹². The people with double-winged language became – big, people with single-winged language became – small.

The French writer 1840-1897 – Alphonse Daudet "La Dernière Classe" "... parce que, quand un peuple tombe esclave, tant qu'il tient bien sa langue, c'est comme s'il tenait la clef de sa prison..."¹³. That is to say Alphonse Daudet in his story called "The Last lesson" mentioned "...when a people are enslaved, as long as they hold fast to their language it is as if they had the key to their prison..."¹⁴.

Indeed, during the soviet period Uzbek language accepted as a "household language" getting the status of the state language, was the sign of the national liberty. Unless it acts as a scientific language in a world evolution as a perfect language it could not find its place in world society. After all, "on the basis of the national language mankind accepted the surrounding world. Language creates an image of the world, as through language it is simplified to

¹¹.Маҳмуд Қошғарий, "Девону луғатит турк" Ўзбекистон Фанлар академияси "Фан" Тошкент 1960-1962 й. 3 жилдли, таржимон ва нашрга тайёрловчи С.М. Муталибов.

¹².Юсуф М., Сайланма Она тилим "Шарк" Тошкент 2018 й. 351-352-б.

¹³.Alphonse Daudet "La Dernière Classe" <http://litgloss.buffalo.edu/daudet/text.php>

¹⁴.Рус тилидан Саиджалол Саидмуродов таржимаси. "Ўзбекистон адабиёти ва санъати газетаси, 2013 йил 42-сон.

perception, realizing the events of the world. When events are not realized in time and are not reflected in our language, they have to get their statement from other languages. As a result, the consciousness of society becomes dependent on other languages"¹⁵. In other words, our nation remains dependent from the perspective of scientific language. So, now saving the Uzbek scientific world from dependence on other academic languages, bringing back the beauty of scientific language of the nation is one of the most important tasks facing the scientists. Otherwise, as we noted, our language will not be able to fly as high as a single-winged bird and to the far-sighted destinations.

Taking a glance at history, we try to draw conclusions about the objective reasons for dependence on the scientific language. In this matter, first of all, it should be noted that no matter under what idea or slogan invaders came to conquer, their main goal is to destroy, rob, humiliate, break the nation, sometimes pushing the way of life back to thousands of years. There were such cases when the population was massacred or their culture and language were completely destroyed. Then the invaders sought to prove themselves in various forms that they were supposedly the "heroes" of this land, that they had "brought from ignorance to enlightenment" the people they had humiliated. We think that our ancestors who have over and over again such suffers, the brutal massacres of the invader, had no other choice than writing their research in a language of the invaders. Those who did not speak Arabic, had their tongue cut off. Al Beruniy wrote that after the Arab conquest, in an attempt to paralyze the local population spiritually-scientifically, they collected and burned all the books up to them in a wide square, and they kept burning for months. *Қайсарни Рум найзасидан, Бағрида доғ узра доғ, Чингузу Боту тигига, Кўкси қалқон ўзбегим...*¹⁶.

In the early days of the Soviet regime, the couscous representatives of our nation, with high scientific potential, and with high national pride – students¹⁷ who returned to from abroad and jadids were brutally massacred. The circumstances, such as the trial of the nation's naive

¹⁵.Алимжонов Б. Ўзбек тилининг ҳозирги ҳолати ва келажги. <http://til.gov.uz/uz/news-and-announcements/anons/161>

¹⁶. Воҳидов Э., Сайланма 1-жилд Ўзбегим қасидаси “Шарқ” Тошкент 2000 й., 200-203-б.

¹⁷ Жовлиев Ж. Қўрқма романи “Asaxiy books” МЧЖ. Тошкент 2020 й. 193-195-бетлар.

children at the expense of the crimes of others , and the sentence of punishment was in a foreign language which was not understandable for the local people, were one of the various manifestations of forcing the local population to "breathe" in the manner of invaders.

By the grace of the Creator, our ancestors acquired not only the invaders language, but also many foreign languages, they could feel the spirit of other languages, feelings of the author of the source, and got extremely complex sciences. As a result: 1) our thinkers have achieved the better study of the sources involved in their scientific direction from the original; 2) they have managed to eliminate the abstractions in science and find the solutions to the problem on a scientific basis; 3) ensured the improvement of a certain field of science. That is why their immortal scientific heritage has come down to us from the depths of thousands of years. Over the centuries, it has become the basis for the new research of scientists around the world.

The phenomenon of mastering foreign languages and feeling its spirit, which has become a tradition from ancestors, seems to be more relevant, especially in the direction of art. For example, it is known that the famous Hafiz of our people received the applause of even the owners of the language by performing masterpieces of different languages in high levels¹⁸.

It is believed that in previous century a number of our scientists as our ancestors did apart from their mother tongue learned arabian, persian, russian, german, french so they could use the scientific resources in its source language.

In a speech dedicated to the 33rd anniversary of the state language our president, quoted from great representative of the nation: Ishaqkhan Tora Ibrat – "let our young people, to make efforts to learn another language, but first cherish their native language, so to express the respect to the mother tongue – as it is love of the motherland" and emphasized that his saying should serve as an important programming that illuminates our life¹⁹. With this, the agenda of the era of globalization when the whole world is in need for our scientists to carry out their research in English, or by the words of enlightened linguists: now English is the "third sacred language" that we have begun to take the field, continuing the tradition of ancestors in the case on language – parallel coverage of his research with the languages demanded by the times as well as in the language of the state, showing that they should act wisely by remembering that "by making contribution to the development of the other language we should not forget to care about our language".

¹⁸.*Ботир Зокиров, Шерали Жўраев, Муяссар Раззоқова, Бобомурод Ҳамдамов, Мансур Тошматов* сингари бир неча ўнлаб саъанткорларнинг репертуари фикримизнинг исботи бўлиши мумкин.

¹⁹ Президент Шавкат Мирзиёев – Тошкент, 2022 йил, 21 октябрь. Спутник.
<https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/5627>

The great scholar polymath, who developed the perfect rules and grammar of the Arabic language in XI century, the founder a huge number of scientific directions. The strength of his knowledge was the reason – to call Abulkosim Muhammad ibn Umar ibn Ahmad – az Zamakhshari (1075-1144) as Jarullakh - neighbor of Allah, the current followers of our compatriot – uzbek academic language have all the opportunities to introduce to the international scale. The problem of implementing it is on our hands.

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